

Research

The moderating effect of national culture on the nexus between green innovation and financial performance: Evidence from Nigeria

Ursule Yvanna Otek Ntsama ^{1*}, Chen Yan¹, Jean François Bakendakan Manga²

¹School of Accounting, Dongbei University of Finance and Economics, China

²University of International Business and Economics, China

Abstract: The main objective of this article is to study the possible presence of non-linear relationships between green innovation and the financial performance of companies by considering possible threshold effects that can be established by the national culture. Our empirical strategy consists in using the panel smooth transition regression model, developed by (1)(Gonzalez et al. 2017). The choice of this model is motivated by the advantages it offers over classical linear models, used in most existing studies assuming that green innovation has an invariable impact on financial performance. Based on the study of a sample of Nigerian companies, the empirical results reveal a U-shaped relationship between green innovation and market value. Our study provides evidence that green product and process innovation is only financially profitable when a threshold level of national culture is achieved.

Keywords: Green Innovation, National Culture, panel smooth transition regression, non-linear relationship.

*Corresponding Author

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1. Introduction

Most recent economic simulations show that the cost of reducing greenhouse gas emissions cannot be kept at a “reasonable” level without using a portfolio of technologies that goes far beyond what is available currently. Radical innovations are particularly needed in the long term and to deal with the risks of major disasters. In their assessments of the cost of climate change and the cost of interventions to limit its consequences, economists have so far largely ignored innovation, ignoring the role that incentives for creation could play. and the dissemination of green technologies. Technology is of course not completely absent from economic thinking, but it is most often considered as an exogenous factor capable of mitigating climate change and allowing us to adapt to its consequences. The arrival and diffusion of new technologies are understood as mechanical and automatic processes. It is impossible in this context to think about the effect of public policies on innovation, and the consequences that these policies could have on the cost and effects of global warming. This article proposes to go beyond this limit of traditional economic reasoning.

While traditional innovation refers to the development of new products, materials, processes, services and organizational forms in order to gain a competitive advantage, green innovation refers to the generation of new ideas, new products, services, processes or management systems that can be used to address environmental issues.

Green innovation has received a particular attention from the business sector due to the growing concern about the state of the environment. Indeed, it is essential that industrial companies, and in particular those in heavily polluting production industries, have a responsibility to protect the environment. The benefits of adapting their processes to protect the environment, companies must also consider the needs of customers and the corporate social responsibility. Many industrial companies have started to implement strategies process-oriented green strategies and product-oriented green strategies. In general, green innovation is often divided into green process innovation and green innovation green product. Previous research has examined the impacts of different types of green innovation, suggesting that green innovation green process and green product innovation are both performance indicators (2)(Xie, Huo, and Zou 2019). The global pro-environmental transition has led companies to engage in green innovations and restructure their business operations to remain competitive and mitigate any adverse effects on the environment. However, the integration of green innovation must align with the strategic objectives of the company to remain sufficiently profitable. Companies must answer the crucial question of whether involvement in green innovation improves their profitability. Surely, green innovation can bring environmental benefits, but the question of whether it can positively impact the financial performance of companies has always been the subject of heated debate among researchers. Over the past few decades, a plethora of research has addressed the association between green innovation practices and firm performance; however, studies reflect a controversial association with mixed and inconclusive results (3)(Przychodzen, Gómez-Bezars, and Przychodzen 2018), which has puzzled practitioners and managers as to what kind of practices and strategies to adopt.

However, much of the literature has ignored the internal mechanisms and conditions contingent relationships between green innovation and business performance such as national culture. National culture plays a potential catalytic role in the establishment of green innovation practices. Thus, we suggest and examine whether national culture represents a transition variable whose level conditions the direction and intensity of the impact of green innovation on financial performance.

2. Theoretical Framework

We characterize the sustainable policies of companies with reference to their stakeholders and consider culture as a component of the institutional environment. Under the double prism of stakeholder theory and institutional theory, we expose the link between green innovation and national culture. In this section, relevant points are discussed, such as green innovation, national culture, social responsibility, and financial performance.

2.1 Green innovation

According to (4)(Peters and Romi 2014) , the way organizations are running, tends to increase their environmental legitimacy. Focusing on the characteristics of hyper connectivity and super intelligence, it is considered that green innovation can improve the commissioning of products and introduce new alternatives in the companies. In addition, studies emphasize green purchasing and show that the advantages of companies in the implementation of ecological production methods are resulting in an improvement of the environment in the form of an elimination of the negative effects of pollution, waste and toxic emissions to provide greater sustainability of the atmosphere. The capacity of companies and their abilities to increase sustainable measures is an absolute necessity (5)(Haseeb et al. 2019) which depends on the capacity of the company and the sector of activity in which it operates. In this regard, the organizations

face several internal and external pressures and limitations that make the process of adopting sustainable technological changes difficult. However, the possible managerial repercussions of the implementation of ecological responsibility measures business and green processes include reducing energy dependence, reducing the use of natural resources, improving monetary settlements and cost reduction. With regard to (6)(Artha and Mulyana 2018), the complementarity between the increase in the market value of the company, the amplified brand image as well as a better awareness of society's expectations in terms of the environment, encourage company management to implement and assimilate more and more innovations in processes such as recycling; in order to reach levels higher efficiency and benefit from a better ecological image thanks to the green methods.

Because of the definition used in this study, green innovation can be divided into four types; green product, process, service, and method innovation. These four types will be used to describe green innovation on itself in more detail. Although, this study will make no further distinction between these types. It is also necessarily to mention that green product innovation completely dominates the other three types of green innovation for incorporating environmental concerns into corporate operations (7)(Chan et al. 2016). But in this section, for the sake of completeness, the four different types of green innovation will be substantiated consecutively.

2.2 Hofstede's Dimensions of National culture

Hofstede's Cultural Dimensions are six dimensions that are internationally recognized for the understanding of cultural differences: Power Distance Index (high versus low); Individualism Versus Collectivism; Masculinity Versus Femininity; Uncertainty Avoidance Index (high versus low); Long-Versus Short-Term Orientation; Indulgence Versus Restraint. Four dimensions fit the research, and in general, researchers have hypothesized that entrepreneurship is facilitated by cultures that are high in individualism, low in uncertainty avoidance, low in power distance, and high in masculinity. Individualism is explained and exemplified by (8)(Hofstede and Minkov 2010) as applying to societies in which the ties for individuals are loose and everyone is expected to look after him.

Uncertainty avoidance is the extent to which the members of a culture feel threatened by ambiguous or unknown situations, (8)(Hofstede and Minkov 2010)

Power distance can be defined as the extent to which less powerful members of a company accept that power is distributed unequally (8)(Hofstede and Minkov 2010).

The masculine dimension is referred to as a society where men are assertive, tough, and focused on material success whereas women are supposed to be more modest, tender, and concerned with the quality of life, according to (8)(Hofstede and Minkov 2010).

3. Theories and Hypotheses

3.1 Relationship between green innovation and financial performance

Innovation has been widely identified as a key aspect of competitiveness and financial returns (9)(Azevedo-Rezende et al. 2019). In the era of the knowledge economy, innovation is an essential source of competitive advantage (10)(Chang 2011). Indeed, innovation allows the creation of "isolation mechanisms" that can protect profit margins while allowing companies to derive advantages in terms of reputation, image, and efficiency in the use of resources. Innovation allows companies to create and deploy their resources and capabilities that support long-term performance. (11)(Garcia, Mendes-Da-Silva, and Orsato 2017) add that successful innovation can make external imitation more difficult, allowing firms to better maintain their advantages. Although higher performance is expected through innovation, empirical studies do not always confirm the presence of a positive relationship (12)(Rosenbusch, Brinckmann, and Bausch 2011).

Similarly, the influence of green innovation on competitiveness has also been studied, but the results are not conclusive, as some studies show via a negative association between them; others, on the other hand, have found a positive relationship. Some empirical research and theoretical perspectives claim that green innovation has a negative effect on business performance. (13)(Driessen et al. 2013) find a significant and negative relationship between green innovation and firm performance. (14)(Caracuel and Ortiz-de-Mandojana 2013) observe that companies using green innovation do not experience increased financial performance compared to companies that are neutral in terms of environmental innovation. Reflecting the complexity of reality, after examining a sample of 2181 firms and nine types of green process innovation, (15)(Doran and Ryan 2016) find that only two of the nine have a positive impact on company performance. 'company. These results are broadly consistent with the traditional economic perspective that green innovation is costly and as such often has a negative or no impact on firm performance.

However, many theoretical arguments and empirical studies support the idea that green innovation is beneficial for the financial performance. According to (16)Porter (1995), green innovation offsets the costs of environmental initiatives through the technological change it stimulates, which can make businesses more competitive. Green innovation drives cost reduction through recycling and waste reduction, while giving product differentiation in the marketplace, allowing companies to reach environmentally conscious consumers and, therefore, benefit from the practice of premium pricing (17)(Tang et al. 2018).

The resource-based theory defines that not all resources are of the same importance and not all of them will become a source of a sustainable competitive advantage. Because, it depends on whether the resources could be imitated or substituted. So, the performance of a firm results from valuable resources that are difficult to obtain and hard to imitate or trade. This explains why firms not always adopt efficient practices from other firms, but rather invest in other sources of performance advantage. Green innovation is such a unique capability and thus a key driver of firm performance within this study. The theory defines that competitive advantage leads a firm to perform better than its competitors, because a firm could have relatively lower operating costs or could differentiate itself. When green innovation is successful it could make imitation more difficult, which allows firms to sustain their competitive advantage longer and thus increase their firm financial performance.

To summarize, the majority of studies with empirical evidence of a relationship between green innovation and firm performance or similar performance factors conclude that there is in fact a positive significant relationship between green innovation and these performance factors. Some studies divide firm performance in more specific firm performance factors and environmental performance is one of them.

H1: there is a positive relationship between green innovation and financial performance.

3.2 Moderating Role of the national culture

The Institutional theory provides a research framework for identifying and studying what promotes the survival and legitimacy of organizational practices (18)(Glover et al. 2014). It explains how culture, the social environment, regulation and their evolution have an impact on decisions concerning green or sustainable activities. (19)(Ball and Craig 2010) show that normative pressures lead companies to be more environmentally conscious and argue that institutional research is needed to understand new ethical values and ecological thinking as well as responses to environmental problems. Institutions define what is appropriate or acceptable (legitimate) and make other actions unacceptable or even unthinkable. Linking this to the study means that one could expect differences for the effect of green innovation on firm performance.

Some research shows a positive relationship, some a negative relationship or even an insignificant relationship between these dimensions and innovation rates. Innovation levels are affected by culture (20)(Cox and Khan 2017), this influence

exists because culture can promote a better or worse innovative environment. Recent studies follow different lines of thought, showing that national culture and innovation still present many research gaps. (Cox and Khan 2017) relate national culture to creativity and innovation, signaling that a more formal understanding of culture and innovation is being developed. Similarly, (21)(Bukowski and Rudnicki 2018) analyze the dimensions of national culture and innovation, highlighting that the dimension individualism alone does not fully justify the role of culture. Thus, the authors point out that long-term orientation and flexibility have a positive influence on innovation; however, this study considered only a few East Asian countries.

3.2.1 Individualism and green innovation

Employees of organizations in more individualistic countries have more freedom to develop or try new products (22)(van Everdingen and Waarts 2003). Previous research merging national culture with innovation presented a positive relationship between individualism and innovation (Cox and Khan 2017). Furthermore, (23)(Prim et al. 2017) explain that, in more independent cultures, citizens have greater autonomy to produce ideas and execute them, boosting innovation performance.

Based on this assumption, the second hypothesis is formulated:

H2a. The higher the individualism levels, the higher the innovation rate.

3.2.2 Power of Distance and green innovation

In cultures with less power distance, there is more trust between hierarchical levels (24)(Kaasa 2016), which provides a freer environment where creativity is boosted and ideas are generated. Considering this, countries that have decentralized structures tend to generate more innovation(Prim et al. 2017). On the one hand, in environments with higher power distance, individuals lose the opportunity to participate in decision-making processes. On the other hand, in environments with low power distance, communication and information exchange is more common. Nevertheless, previous research indicates that lower power distance boost innovation rate ((25)Herbig & Dunphy, 1998; (26)Hussler, 2004; (27)Rinne, Steel, & Fairweather, 2012).

Considering that, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H2b. The lower the power distance, the higher the innovation rate.

3.2.3 Uncertainty avoidance and green innovation

Research that relates this dimension to innovation (28)(Andrijauskienė and Dumčiuvienė 2017; Kaasa 2016) mostly found that the relation between uncertainty avoidance and innovation is negative, which means that the lower the uncertainty avoidance, the higher the innovation rates. (van Everdingen and Waarts 2003) emphasize that high uncertainty avoidance imply that companies will not take unnecessary risks; they will adopt innovations only if their value has already been proved in the market.

H2c. The lower the uncertainty avoidance, the higher the innovation rate

3.2.4 Masculinity and green innovation

Considering Hofstede's definition, masculinity tends to promote more competition and femininity more cooperation. In this way, an environment that facilitates information exchange would possibly be more innovative. According to (Cox and Khan 2017), female societies focus on people and cooperation, and by doing so they provide a more favorable environment for innovation. Thus, we propose our third hypothesis:

H2d. The lower the masculinity level, the higher the innovation rate.

4. Research Methodology

4.1 Variables Description

The research is focused on investigating the effects of national culture on the relation between green innovation and financial performance. During our analysis, we used 350 african companies listed on stock exchange from 2011 to 2020 (10 years). All data used in this study are collected from the Thomson Reuters Datastream (Refinitiv) database, which offers financial data as well as environmental, social and governance (ESG) information for more than 4,500 companies worldwide.

We use Tobin's Q, a market-based measure, to assess financial performance. One of the main reasons for our preference for Tobin's Q is that this measure is a forward-looking assessment of financial performance since the stock price is a key component of its calculation. Therefore, it is expected to better capture the long-term financial benefits of green innovation practices and policies.

Green innovation, our main explanatory variable, is expressed by the variable ProdInno to measure green product innovation and the two variables EmiRed and ResUse to measure green process innovation. The "Product Innovation" (ProdInno) measures the commitment and effectiveness of a company's management in supporting the research and development of eco-efficient products or services. It reflects the ability of a company to reduce environmental costs for its customers, and therefore to create new market opportunities thanks to new technologies and new environmental processes or to eco-designed, dematerialized and long-life products. The "Emission Reduction" (EmiRed) category measures the commitment and effectiveness of a company's management to reduce environmental emissions in production and operational processes. It reflects a company's ability to reduce air emissions, waste, hazardous waste, water discharges, spills or their impacts on biodiversity and to partner with environmental organizations to reduce the environmental impact of the business in the local or wider community. The "ResourceUse" (ResUse) category measures the commitment and effectiveness of a company's management to efficiently use natural resources in the production process. It reflects a company's ability to reduce the use of materials, energy or water, and find more eco-efficient solutions by improving supply chain management.

In addition, we introduce three control variables. The first variable is MTB ratio (market-to-book) which reflects the real market value of equity. This variable is calculated by the ratio between the company's market capitalization and the book amount of its equity. The second variable is TASSET (It designates the size of the company and it is measured by the natural logarithm of the total assets). The third variable is Leverage (LEV). It refers to financial leverage and is measured by the ratio of total debt to total assets.

We used panel data as a measurement to assess the influence of independent variables on a given dependent variable considering a set of observations over time. The cluster analysis technique was then used to classify the countries according to their culture and innovation similarities. The Ward method and Euclidean distance were used to measure the distances between clusters as the most common methods employed in cluster analysis for comparing the similarity between two or more objects.

4.2 Methodology

To test the nonlinear relationship between green innovation and financial performance, we use the panel smooth transition regression (PSTR) by (Gonzalez et al. 2017). Thus, the PSTR model makes it possible to grasp the potential non-linear dynamic between green innovation and financial performance, i.e. the determination of a "threshold" value of environmental performance, thus allowing a smooth change in the coefficient of the regression slope when switching from one regime to another. The PSTR model presents itself as a more flexible and reliable model than traditional

econometric models based on linear regressions because it allows capturing the unobserved and time-invariant effects of companies in the modeling of data from panel.

Before testing the PSTR model, it is essential to test the non-linearity hypothesis using LM Fisher test (table 2).

5. Results Analysis and Discussion

5.1 Descriptive Statistic

The descriptive statistics are presented in table 1

Table 1 Descriptive Statistic

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
<i>Panel A: Financial Performance Variables</i>					
TQ	3,500	0.6758	0.5718	0.161	8.407
<i>Panel B: Green Innovation Variables</i>					
ProdInn	3,500	55.551	10.102	41	72.67
EmiRed	3,500	56.881	0.2289	56.26	57.32
ResUse	3,500	58.524	5.9638	43.39	67.28
<i>Panel C: Moderating Variables</i>					
POD	3,500	38.787	5.3955	25	44.89
MAS	3,500	55.667	4.063	49.79	63.66
COLL	3,500	78.889	4.085	70	84.34
UNA	3,500	50.632	3.5457	42.45	57.16
<i>Control Variables</i>					
Lev	3,500	0.687	0.8988	-0.541	19.71
MTB	3,500	0.6632	0.4319	0.01	2.117
TASSET	3,500	7.3414	0.9056	3.304	9.964

5.2 Unit Root test

Insofar as we should consider the possible existence of unobservable heterogeneities between individuals in our sample, in order to test the presence of a unit root, we use two different tests. The first is the test of (29)(Im, Pesaran, and Shin 2003) (IPS) which allows heterogeneities to be considered under the alternative hypothesis of the absence of a unit root. The second test is the test of (30)(Levin, Lin, and James Chu 2002) (LLC), which retains rather a homogeneity of the panel under the alternative hypothesis.

Table 2 Unit Root Test

Variables	LLC		IPS	
	Level	Dif	Level	Dif
TQ	-3.931***	-5.614***	-11.421***	-10.711***
ProdInn	-3.131***	-6.941***	-4.416**	-10.974***
EmiRed	-4.154***	-7.964***	-7.648***	-10.679***
ResUse	-3.037***	-5.433***	-7.713***	-13.316***

POD	-4.648***	-7.677***	-11.641***	-14.597***
MAS	-3.733***	-5.910***	-9.483***	-15.747***
COLL	-3.133***	-5.003***	-10.944***	-16.981***
UNA	-5.181***	-8.937***	-10.430***	-16.211***
Lev	-1.931**	-2.452***	-9.437***	-17.401***
MTB	-3.188***	-4.611***	-6.054***	-11.145***
TASSET	-2.746**	-4.247***	-6.327***	-10.546***

Notes: *** significant at 1% and ** significant at 5%. LLC and IPS are respectively the tests of Levin, Lin and Chu (2002) and of Im, Pesaran and Shin (2003).

5.3 PSTR Model

The results of the PSTR model estimates are presented in Table 3. The estimated threshold level of the transition variable is of the order of \hat{c} . It makes it possible to distinguish two extreme regimes of the national culture proxies: (1) a low regime where the estimated coefficients of the variables EmiRed, ResUse, and ProdInn are lower than the threshold value, and (2) a high regime where the estimated coefficients of the variables EmiRed, ResUse, and ProdInn are above this threshold value. Our results show that the relationship between the two types of green innovation and financial performance is not monotonically linear. Indeed, we find that green innovation in terms of processes and products has a negative and significant impact on financial performance when the level of national culture proxies is below the estimated threshold. Once this threshold has been reached and exceeded, under the high regime of each national culture variables, the influence of the three variables of green innovation on financial performance becomes significantly positive.

Finally, our results demonstrate that the relationship between green innovation and financial performance is not linear and monotonous, but that it is much better described by a U-shaped relationship.

TABLE 3 The results of regression analysis without moderation effect in model A & model B present moderation of national culture in green innovation and firm performance

VARIABLES	TQ				
	(01)	(02)	(03)	(04)	(05)
	H3b				
ProdInn	0.009*** (0.003)			0.037** (0.019)	
EmiRed		0.036** (0.108)			1.890* (0.839)
ResUse			0.025** (0.012)		
ProdInn*POD	0.025*** (0.007)	0.439*** (0.188)	0.045** (0.016)	0.058*** (0.013)	0.056*** (0.591)
EmiRed*POD	0.039*** (0.013)			0.061*** (0.011)	
ResUse*POD		0.735*** (0.305)			0.078*** (0.010)
ProdInn*MAS			0.140** (0.017)		
EmiRed*MAS		-0.013*** (0.007)			-0.034** (0.015)
ResUse*MAS			-0.021** (0.013)		
ProdInn*COLL	0.072*** (0.012)			0.211*** (0.013)	
EmiRed*COLL		0.322*** (0.006)			1.053*** (0.013)
ResUse*COLL			0.702*** (0.000)		
ProdInn*UNA	0.031**			0.088**	

	(0.011)			(0.036)	
EmiRed*UNA		0.606**			0.202**
		(0.209)			(0.019)
ResUse*UNA			0.201**		
			(0.019)		
LEV	0.315**	0.328**	0.174**	0.244*	0.279**
	(0.135)	(0.135)	(0.140)	(0.177)	(0.178)
MTB	0.454***	0.465***	0.327**	0.372**	0.409**
	(0.134)	(0.134)	(0.139)	(0.127)	(0.175)
TASSET	-0.016**	-0.026**	-0.013**	0.024**	0.015**
	(0.002)	(0.002)	(0.003)	(0.005)	(0.005)
<hr/>					
PTSR Parameters					
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Threshold ©					
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57.36***					
<hr/>					
(9.41)					
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*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

6. Conclusion

The main objective of this article was to study the non-linear relationship between green innovation and the financial performance of the company while integrating the threshold effects established by the level of Hofstede's dimensions of national culture. For this, unlike previous empirical studies, which use traditional parametric estimation methods, we employed the PSTR nonlinear regression model to detect the dynamics of nonlinearity between the variables and demonstrate the existence of regime change behaviour, due to threshold effects, caused by the moderating variable. Unlike previous studies that have used structural equation models extensively, especially to construct variables related to green innovation, our study uses information on green innovation in products and processes from the Thomson Reuters Datastream ASSET4 ESG data.

Our research highlights the importance of considering national culture as a crucial part of business strategy for achieving the triple bottom line objectives

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